

NON-CONTRACTUAL REGULATION OF LEGAL RELATIONS FOR PROTECTION OF RIGHTS OF SUBJECTS OF COMMERCIAL CONFIDENTIAL INFORMATION

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Annotation: In this article is discussed the role of a trade secrets in civil legal relations by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is known, that the role of objects of intellectual activity has immeasurably increased, as they became along with traditional material objects full participants of economic turnover. In this article is also given a complex analyses of essence and legal nature of trade secrets as the object of legal relations and elaborated decisions to improve acting legislation regulating present sphere.

Key words: information, confidential information, legal regime, types of information, methods of protection of information.

An important condition for the innovative development of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan today is not only the recognition of civil rights to trade secrets, but also the availability of a mechanism for their reliable civil legal protection. Existing in legal science approaches to solving the problems of information protection are very diverse. In many publications devoted to the study of trade secret problems, the emphasis is placed on organizational and managerial, technical, administrative, criminal and other aspects of legal protection of information and does not pay due attention to civil law issues of their provision. Meanwhile, lawyers, as the analysis of legal practice shows, perceive the protection of trade secrets through the prism of civil law means.

Analysis of the legislation governing relations in the field of trade secrets and trade secrets (know-how), as well as the practice of its implementation convinces that it is very problematic to actually protect the violated rights to trade secrets today. This is because the mechanism of protection of trade secret rights proposed in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Trade Secrets" is not yet sufficiently developed in relation to modern conditions and does not meet the needs of legal practice, does not fully guarantee the protection of subjective rights and interests of business entities in this area. Commercial organizations lack a methodology for calculating and proving losses associated with the violation of trade secret

rights. The developed general methodology of damages does not take into account the specifics of protection of rights in this area. Due to the imperfection of the current mechanism, there is an insignificant number of applications of right holders, whose rights have been violated, to economic courts with claims for compensation for losses caused by the disclosure of protected information, and their lack of practical skills in applying other methods of protection of civil rights.

Commercialization of the results of scientific research, increasing attention of business to the use of innovations in their activities requires solving the problem of selection and effective application in economic practice of ways to protect the rights to trade secrets. The methods of protection of civil rights developed in civil science are not always suitable for such an object as information constituting a trade secret, and without certain adaptation can not be used in practice. Recommendations contained in the literature are sometimes of a general nature and do not take into account the specifics of offenses committed in the circulation of information. Therefore, in our opinion, it is important to study the ways of protecting the rights to trade secrets at the level of corporate relations and in the process of contractual and non-contractual work related to the transfer of information, performance of work (services) in the information sphere.

The traditional development of civil law is based on the fact that contractual and non-contractual (so-called tort) liability developed in parallel. Fundamentally new varieties of civil liability do not yet exist. However, in each separate area of civil law relations there are specific sets of civil law sanctions. They are composed due to different combinations of sanctions already known in civil law, or periodically specific sanctions are provided for certain relations, the nature of which, especially at the initial stage of their introduction is debatable. There may be different grounds of liability, subjects of liability.

The obligation of third parties not to violate the trade secret regime is a civil law obligation. Therefore, its violation entails civil liability. The law explicitly imposes the obligation to compensate for losses on persons who obtained undisclosed information by illegal methods. This also applies to persons who disclosed it contrary to the contract, without legal grounds, using it. Therefore, such liability will naturally be non-contractual in nature and will exist in parallel with contractual liability.

Despite the commonality of contractual and non-contractual types of civil liability it is necessary to note the differences. Tort liability is traditionally a

separate institute of civil law. It has its own peculiarities, which, first of all, are expressed in the significant predominance of peremptory norms in the composition of the legislation [3].

As for non-contractual, or so-called “tort obligations”, the legal literature uses the concepts of “obligations due to infliction of harm” and “liability for infliction of harm” as identical in meaning, and in both concepts the basic term is “liability” [4].

This provision is reflected in Chapter 57 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan – “Obligations due to the infliction of harm”, Article 985 of which is devoted to the general grounds of liability for the infliction of harm. This shows that there are no contradictions between these concepts and that they are related to each other [1].

The totality of norms enshrined in Chapter 57 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan “Obligations due to the infliction of harm” covers a range of relations much wider than those in the course of which civil liability is realized. Tort liability is based on the fact of wrongful infliction of harm. Obligations to compensate for harm may cover cases of rightful infliction of harm, as well as provide for the obligation to compensate for harm caused through the fault of others. The existence of the fact of infliction of harm in the predominant number of cases determines the existence of the grounds of liability for its infliction, including the liability of another subject.

In obligations arising from the infliction of harm, liability is incurred on the general grounds set forth in Article 985 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, according to which “harm caused by unlawful acts (inaction) to a citizen's person or property, as well as harm caused to a legal entity, shall be compensated by the person who caused the harm, in full, including lost profit”.

As a rule, in these cases, liability arises on the basis of the fact of the offense, and it is with the emergence of an obligation due to the infliction of harm that liability, i.e. the possibility of applying certain sanctions to the offender, also appears. By means of tort obligations, the situation that existed before the offense is restored [5].

As a general rule, wrongful conduct and guilt are necessary conditions of civil liability for all types of civil offenses, both contractual and non-contractual. In order to impose civil liability on the debtor by non-fulfillment or improper fulfillment of the obligation in cases where the creditor has suffered damage or losses, it is necessary to have a causal link between the unlawful behavior of the debtor and the resulting consequences.

Article 333 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for guilt as a general basis of civil liability for breach of obligations. The provisions of this article impose strict requirements on a debtor wishing to prove his innocence and thereby exempt himself from liability. Guilt expresses the attitude of the offender to the responsibility imposed on him by law or contract. According to the norms of civil law, the debtor will be liable only if he is guilty of breach of obligations. In this case, the “presumption of guilt” plays an important role: the debtor may be released from liability if he proves that there is no fault on his part in the breach of obligation.

The main measure of civil liability applied to the violator of the right to confidential commercial information, both in domestic and foreign practice, is to impose on him the obligation to compensate the injured party for losses, which may include (if the law or the contract of the parties does not provide for compensation of losses in a smaller amount) both real damage and lost profits. In order to apply this measure of liability to the infringer, the owner of confidential information whose right has been violated must prove that the information obtained by the infringer meets the requirements established by law for information constituting confidential information and that the infringer gained access to such information in an unlawful manner, as well as justify the amount of damages [2].

In the case of unlawful access to information constituting a trade secret, in our opinion, it would be possible to demand a judicial injunction to prohibit the infringer from disclosing and using the information to which he has illegally gained access. Such a prohibition for unscrupulous infringers should arise automatically by virtue of the law. Accordingly, this provision should be reflected in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Commercial Secrets”.

Such a sanction could impose on the infringer of the right to a trade secret the obligation to pay monetary compensation to the owner of confidential information, whose right has been violated, in an amount to be determined by the court within the limits established by law in case it is impossible to determine the exact amount of losses to be compensated by the infringer.

In order to implement this provision, it is advisable to enshrine in the legislation a provision according to which a person who illegally and in bad faith gained access to information constituting confidential commercial information of another person may be compelled by court order to pay monetary compensation to the victim in the amount determined by the court based on the circumstances that led to such access.

An unscrupulous infringer should be held liable for unlawful access to information constituting confidential commercial information of another person, even if the information unlawfully accessed is similar to information previously obtained independently and in good faith.

Another point that I would like to emphasize is the problem of exemption from liability for infringement of rights to confidential commercially valuable information of bona fide purchasers, since not in all cases access to information constituting a trade secret is illegal. In this case, bona fide purchasers are persons who did not know and did not have reasonable grounds to believe that the information to which they gained access constitutes a trade secret of another person, including those who gained access to the information as a result of accident or error [6].

At the request of the owner of confidential commercial information, such a bona fide acquirer should be obliged to maintain the confidentiality of such commercially valuable information. Failure to fulfill this obligation should already entail liability, since in this case the right of the holder himself to the information constituting a trade secret is violated.

In our view, the owner of information constituting a trade secret may assert a claim for unjust enrichment against a person who in good faith obtained access to such information, unless that bona fide purchaser proves that he obtained exactly the same information as a result of his research. If he fails to prove it, unjust enrichment will be expressed in the amounts that the bona fide acquirer would have had to pay to the holder of the trade secret information if he had obtained the right to use the trade secret information under a contract with the holder.

In this connection, the owner of information constituting a trade secret, who has no possibility to prevent its use by a bona fide purchaser, should demand the conclusion with the bona fide purchaser of an agreement on granting the right to use the information constituting a trade secret, or an agreement on granting the right to use the information constituting a trade secret, on terms determined by the parties, and in the absence of these terms – by court decision.

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